

REACTIVE ATOMIZATION AND DEPOSITION PROCESSING OF Ni₃Al/Y₂O₃ USING N₂-O₂ ATOMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

A relatively new processing technique, Reactive Atomization and Deposition (RAD), is developed to synthesize dispersion-strengthened MMCs and monolithic materials. In this process, atomization, in-situ reaction, and consolidation are combined into a single step using spray atomization and deposition equipment with N₂-O₂ atomization gas. The matrix material is selected to be Ni₃Al+Y+B alloy system. Anticipated dispersoids, such as Y₂O₃, Al₂O₃ and NiO are identified by transmission electron microscopy. The thermal stability of the RAD processed materials increases with increasing oxygen content in the atomization gas. The reaction kinetics between droplet and atomization gas are studied and mass transfer through the oxide film is suggested to be the rate-limiting step. Processing maps are used in the present work to illustrate the effect of processing variables on the resultant microstructure.

Keywords: rapid solidification, in-situ reaction and dispersion-strengthening

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of inert additions to improve the elevated-temperature mechanical properties of metals was first reported in 1910 by W.D. Coolidge [1] for thoriated tungsten. It was not until 1946 that the next major step in the evolution of oxide-dispersion-hardened alloys was accomplished with the development of sintered aluminum powders (SAP) by a Swiss research group [2]. The principal accomplishment of this work was the incorporation of the dispersoid, Al₂O₃, into the matrix aluminum powders during a grinding operation. The preparation and properties of SAP materials have been reviewed in detail by Bloch [3] and will not be repeated here. One of the important characteristics of these dispersion strengthened materials is the experimentally observed increase in strength with increasing oxide content up to approximately 12 wt.% - 15 wt.% Al₂O₃. Shortly thereafter, the application of the mechanical alloying technique to produce dispersion-strengthened superalloys was first reported by J.S. Benjamin in 1970 [4]. The available scientific literature demonstrates that over the last two decades a large number of oxide-dispersion-strengthened (ODS) systems have been successfully developed using a variety of techniques. The elevated-temperature strength and thermal stability typically associated with ODS alloys are generally derived from the presence of refractory oxide (Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃) particles less than 0.1µm in size, which are evenly distributed within an alloy powder particle in such a manner as to lead to interparticle spacings of less than 0.5 µm in a consolidated product. This dislocation barrier effect has also been reported in a SiC reinforced aluminum metal matrix composite (MMC) prepared by powder metallurgy [5]. In this study it was suggested that dislocations are pinned by the fine incoherent oxide particles that are present in the Al matrix, as a result of the manufacture of SiC_p-6061 Al by powder metallurgy. Moreover, the authors reported that the threshold stress for creep in the composite increased in the presence of oxide dispersoids.

In view of the aforementioned findings, a relatively new processing technique, Reactive Atomization and Deposition (RAD), is developed to combine atomization, reaction and consolidation into a single step process to synthesize dispersion-strengthened MMCs and monolithic materials. In this process, molten matrix is atomized into a dispersion of micron-sized droplets by high velocity gas jets and subsequently deposited onto a suitable substrate or surface. By carefully selecting alloying additions and reactive gas combinations on the basis of thermodynamic considerations, it is possible to use RAD processing to synthesize materials containing in-situ dispersoids, such as carbides, nitrides and oxides. A schematic diagram of the experimental apparatus used in the present study is shown in

Figure 1. As will be demonstrated below, $N_2 - O_2$ gas mixtures as atomization gas, for example, may readily be used to form oxide particles in a metallic matrix. Nevertheless, the synthesis approach described in the present work offers the opportunity for in-situ, continuous control over alloy composition and chemical reaction between atomized droplets and reactive atomization gas.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing experimental apparatus of RAD processing.

Table 1. Experimental variables used in the present study

Variables	Experimental
Material	Ni 11%Al 1-2%Y 0.02%B (wt.)
Atomization Gas	$N_2 + O_2$ *
Atomization Pressure	2.41 MPa (350 psi)
Pouring Temperature	1600°C
Melt Flow Rate	21 g/s
Gas Flow Rate	9 g/s (estimated) .
Flight Distance	27.9 cm**

* N_2 ; $N_2 + 5 \text{ wt.}\% O_2$; $N_2 + 15 \text{ wt.}\% O_2$; $N_2 + 35 \text{ wt.}\% O_2$

** The substrate was displaced vertically during deposition

2. EXPERIMENTAL

In the present study, a Ni_3Al intermetallic compound was selected as the matrix material as a result of recent interest in this class of material for elevated-temperature applications [7]. For the preparation of the experimental material, pure nickel and aluminum with an atomic ratio of 3:1 were placed in a zirconia crucible. In addition, 0.02 wt.% B was added in a form of Ni_2B to improve room temperature ductility on the basis of Aoki and Liu's work [8,9]. Also, 1-2 wt.% Y was added to enhance the reactivity of the alloy and ultimately form Y_2O_3 dispersoids. The Ni-Al-B-Y mixture was melted under a nitrogen atmosphere up to a maximum temperature of 1600-1650°C, where it was held

for 10 minutes. Then, the molten alloy was delivered to an atomizer by a ceramic delivery tube, where it was atomized using either N_2 or N_2 - XO_2 gas mixtures (where $X=0.05, 0.15$ and 0.35 in weight). The experimental parameters used in the present study are listed in Table 1. Following RAD processing, X-ray diffraction and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were conducted to ascertain the formation of Ni_3Al intermetallic compound, and the presence and type of oxide particles. In addition, chemical analyses were conducted to determine the composition of the RAD processed materials and the extent of oxidation during atomization. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was also conducted on the as-deposited materials. Finally, to investigate the thermal stability of the spray deposited materials, the RAD processed materials were annealed at $1200^\circ C$ for 2-8 hours, and grain size measurements were conducted on both as-deposited and annealed materials.

3. RESULTS

X-ray diffraction analysis results revealed the presence of both fundamental lines from planes of unmixed indices and superlattice lines from planes of mixed indices, which indicated that the matrix is indeed the Ni_3Al intermetallic compound [10]. Also, traces of Al_2O_3 and Ni_2Y were observed in the materials atomized using $N_2 - 5$ wt.% O_2 and $N_2 - 15$ wt.% O_2 gas mixtures. It is worth noting that a significant amount of Ni and a small amount of NiO phase were observed in the material atomized using $N_2 - 35$ wt.% O_2 .

Bright field and dark field TEM micrographs of the materials atomized using $N_2 - 5$ wt.% O_2 are shown in Fig. 2; Y_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 and Ni_2Y were identified by Selective Area Diffraction (SAD) analysis. Qualitative analysis, conducted on the basis of TEM, revealed that the volume fraction of oxide particles increased with increasing the content of O_2 in the $N_2 - O_2$ atomizing gas. Scanning electron microscopy results (Fig. 3) revealed the presence of the Ni_3Al intermetallic as matrix and a Ni-rich disordered phase as secondary phase, consistent with the X-ray results. This phenomenon was also observed by Zhang [11] and Morris [12].

Figure 2. Transmission electron micrographs of Ni_3Al atomized using N_2 -5 wt.% O_2 .

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrograph of as-deposited Ni₃Al intermetallic compound atomized using N₂-35 wt.% O₂.

Figure 4. The dependence of grain size on annealing time at a temperature of 1200°C.
 (Δ grain size = annealed grain size - as-deposited grain size)

The RAD processed materials were subsequently annealed at 1200°C under inert gas protection. The results, summarized in Figure 4, revealed that the grain size of the N₂ and N₂-5% O₂-RAD materials increased with increasing annealing time. The grain size of the N₂-15% O₂-RAD material, however, remained relatively unchanged for the annealing conditions used herein. This behavior is thought to be due to the large volume fraction of oxide dispersoids present in this material. It was not possible to conduct similar studies on the N₂ - 35% O₂ RAD material as a result of the large volume fraction of porosity that was present in this material. Further work is continuing to provide insight into this phenomenon.

The chemical analysis results, summarized in Table 2, revealed that the total amount of Y present in the RAD material was only 30% of the nominal composition. This phenomenon, although not thoroughly understood, may be attributable to reactions between Y in the melt and the ceramic crucible. Further work is continuing in this area. The O₂ content results shown in Table 2 reveal that the total amount of O₂ present in RAD materials atomized with N₂ - 5 wt.% O₂ and N₂ - 15 wt.% O₂ ranged from 0.15-0.20 wt.%. The total amount of O₂ present in the materials atomized with N₂ - 35 wt.% O₂, however, was 2.38 wt.%. It is worth noting that the material prepared using N₂ - 35 wt.% O₂ was so thin and porous that the measured amount of O₂ might not be indicative of the actual oxygen content in the material.

Table 2. Chemical compositions of Ni₃Al atomized by different gas mixtures

Sample	Atomization Gas	Al [wt.%]	Y [wt.%]	O [wt.%]	B [wt.%]	Ni [wt.%]
#270	N ₂ +35%O ₂	9.07	0.58	2.38	0.034	balance
#213	N ₂ +15%O ₂	10.9	0.07	0.15	0.022	balance
#209	N ₂ +5%O ₂	10.9	0.29	0.20	0.022	balance
#211	N ₂	11.0	0.30	0.03	0.021	balance

4. DISCUSSIONS AND ANALYSES

The possible reactions and corresponding standard free energies of formation (ΔG°) relevant to the Ni-Al-Y-O system at a temperature of 1227°C are [13,14]:

- (1) $\text{Ni} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 = \text{NiO}$ -108.4 kJ/mol
- (2) $2\text{Al} + \frac{3}{2}\text{O}_2 = \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -1146.9 kJ/mol
- (3) $3\text{NiO} + 2\text{Al} = 3\text{Ni} + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -821.7 kJ/mol
- (4) $2\text{Y} + \frac{3}{2}\text{O}_2 = \text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ -1482.1 kJ/mol
- (5) $3\text{NiO} + 2\text{Y} = 3\text{Ni} + \text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ -1156.9 kJ/mol

The magnitude of ΔG° for the reactions listed above, suggests that thermodynamically, Y₂O₃ is the most stable oxide. The X-ray results, however, revealed trace amounts of Al₂O₃ in the materials atomized using N₂ - 5 wt.% O₂ and N₂ - 15 wt.% O₂ and a small amount of NiO in the materials atomized using N₂ - 35 wt.% O₂. This apparent discrepancy may be rationalized on the basis of the characteristics of the relevant reaction kinetics. It is possible that Y atoms did not have sufficient time to diffuse to the surface and react with O₂, and oxidation of Al dominated the reaction. In related studies, some investigators have studied the selective oxidation behavior in different alloy systems. For example, in the Al-Mg system, the accelerated oxidation of molten alloy persists only as long as sufficient Mg is present to support the formation of MgO or MgAl₂O₄. Once the oxidation rate surpasses the consumption of Mg, α -Al₂O₃ become the predominant oxidation product [15].

To obtain a high volume fraction of evenly distributed oxide particles in the RAD materials, it would be desirable for oxidation reactions to occur evenly throughout each droplet (e.g., internal and external oxidation), instead of oxidizing primarily on the droplet surface. However, on the basis of thermodynamic considerations, internal oxidation in a single droplet is possible only when the partial pressure of O_2 , p_{O_2} , is lower than 6×10^{-9} atm.^[16] Hence, in view of the relatively high concentration of O_2 used in the gas mixtures, as well as the relatively short flight time of droplets^[17], it is most likely that external oxidation dominates the ensuing reactions. Fortunately, even if surface oxidation dominates the reaction of the droplets, the violent impact of the partially solidified droplets during deposition would lead to the formation of a relatively homogeneous distribution of oxide particles in the RAD materials. This mechanism is illustrated schematically in Fig. 5. Hence, the RAD processing may be readily utilized to synthesize oxide-dispersion-strengthened materials containing a relatively homogeneous distribution of oxide phases.

Figure 5. Schematic of oxide-film fragmentation

Regarding microstructure, the interparticle spacing, λ , can be estimated using the expression:

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{lt}{f}}$$

suggested by Fullman and Kelly^[18,19]. It may be assumed that after deposition, the oxide particles are in the shape of platelets whose average thickness, t , and length, l , are 4 and 50 nm, respectively^[20]. The volume fraction of oxide, f , can be estimated to be 0.59% for the $N_2+15\% O_2$ material, on the basis of the result shown in Table 2. The magnitude of λ , is then calculated to be 180 nm.

Regarding the kinetics of the reactions of a droplet with the surrounding gas, there are five possible mechanisms that need to be considered. (1) Mass transfer of oxygen in the gas boundary layer surrounding the droplet, (2) Adsorption of oxygen atoms at the surface of the droplets, (3) Mass transfer of oxygen through the oxide film, (4) Selective chemical reaction of oxygen with reactive elements, (5) Mass transfer of oxygen in the droplet. These five possible mechanisms are discussed

in detail elsewhere [21]. Mass transfer of oxygen through the oxide film was concluded to be the rate limiting step among them.

A processing map for RAD processing was developed to establish the quantitative relationship that exists between the oxide film and the oxygen concentration [22]. The map shown in Fig. 6 reveals isopleth lines of oxide film thickness. The graph may be divided into three primary zones. In the zone on the left hand side, the thickness of the oxide film is less than x_l , and in the zone on the right hand side, an oxide film thicker than x_r may be anticipated, and in the middle zone the thickness of the oxide film falls between x_l and x_r . From left to right, the thickness of the oxide film increases, as denoted by the direction of the arrow. It is evident that the partial pressure of oxygen necessary to produce an oxide layer with a given thickness decreases with increasing droplet temperature. This may be attributed to the fact that both the diffusion rate of oxygen and the oxidation reaction rate increase rapidly with increasing temperature. On the other hand, at a constant droplet temperature, the thickness of the oxide film will increase with increasing partial pressure of oxygen. However, the effect of the partial pressure of oxygen on the oxide film thickness is less significant than that of the temperature, since, as previously mentioned, the diffusion of oxygen is the dominant rate-controlling step, and increasing temperature can effectively increase the diffusivity of oxygen. In general, either increasing the droplet temperature at a constant oxygen partial pressure, or increasing the oxygen partial pressure at a constant droplet temperature, will enhance oxide formation kinetics, thereby increasing the thickness of the associated oxide film.

The aforementioned analysis suggests that mass transfer through the oxide film is the rate limiting step for the formation of oxide particles during RAD processing. However, the above analysis necessitated various assumptions that are worth noting. For example, because the time spent by an average sized droplet from the point of atomization to the point of impact is milliseconds, initially,

Figure 6. Proposed processing map for a reaction time of 1 ms.

there may be no oxide film formed, or the oxide film may be discontinuous. In this case, the rate of chemical reaction, instead of diffusion, may become the rate limiting step. Accordingly, there are further theoretical analyses presently being conducted to evaluate the role of heat, mass and momentum transfer, and chemical reaction kinetics, during RAD processing. The results observed in the present work, however, do suggest that the RAD processing methodology may be effectively used to synthesize metallic matrices containing a distribution of nanometric oxide particles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) On the basis of thermodynamic considerations, Ni₃Al-Y alloy and N₂-O₂ gas mixtures were selected to synthesize oxide-dispersion-strengthened materials using RAD processing.
- (2) Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃ were observed by TEM; the volume fraction of oxide particles increased with increasing content of O₂ in the N₂-O₂ atomizing gas.
- (3) The thermal stability of RAD processed materials increased with increasing content of O₂ in the N₂-O₂ atomizing gas.
- (4) On the basis of kinetic analysis, it is suggested that mass transfer through the oxide film is the rate-limiting step for the formation of oxide particles during RAD processing. The processing map has shown that the thickness of oxide film increases with temperature of droplet and oxygen partial pressure in atomization gas.

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